

NURSE MOTIVATION IN ADMISSION A NEW PATIENTS AT MENUR PSYCIATRIC MENTAL HOSPITAL SURABAYA

Suprianto ^{1*}, Hadi Purwanto ², Krisnawati ¹

¹ Diploma Program of Nursing (Campus Sidoarjo), Health Polytechnic of Surabaya, Ministry of Health Republic Indonesia

² Diploma Program of Nursing (Campus Tuban), Health Polytechnic of Surabaya, Ministry of Health Republic Indonesia

***Correspondence:**

Suprianto

Email: siperpri73@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background: Mental disorders are defined as mental states that make people unable to relate to reality (Stuart, 2016). Mental disorder is a disease that is becoming and becoming a global trend globally, 1 in 4 people suffer from mental disorders both in developed and developing countries.

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to explore the motivation of nurses in the admission of new patients at Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital Surabaya.

Methods: This type of research is a qualitative research with an interpretive phenomenological approach. Information was obtained by interviewing 12 nurses as participants in the activity of admitting new patients.

Results: Nurses are encouraged to engage in new patient admission activities influenced by two external factors, namely the existence of competence and autonomy that has the value of incentives and internal factors, namely the drive within themselves to maintain the quality of nursing services and maintain social relations with superiors.

Discussion: Mastery expertise and skills of the new admissions nurse are needed to strengthen the independence of the nursing team leader in conducting new patient admissions and the nursing team members' self-understanding of their involvement in the social environment of the patient care room to foster initiative to engage in the process of admission a new patient.

Key words: Admission of new patients, competence, autonomy, social relations.

INTRODUCTION

Mental disorders are defined as mental states that make people unable to relate to reality (Stuart, 2016). Mental disorder is a disease that is becoming and becoming a global trend globally, 1 in 4 people suffer from mental disorders both in developed

and developing countries. This disease can occur to anyone, anytime and anywhere. Riskesdas 2018 data shows that 15.7 - 16.2% of people experience psychiatric problems (depression and mental emotional disorders). While the prevalence of mental disorders (Schizophrenia and Psychosis)

ranges from 6.2 - 7.1%. This mental disorder requires treatment in the health service unit.

Schizophrenia is a mental disorder characterized by impaired thought processes and weak emotional responses. This situation is generally manifested in the form of hallucinations, paranoia, false beliefs or thoughts that are incompatible with the real world and are built on elements that are not based on logic, and are accompanied by significant social and work dysfunction. Early symptoms usually appear during young adulthood, with a global lifetime prevalence of around 0.3% - 0.7% (Townsend, 2015).

People with mental disorders, both schizophrenia and psychosis in general can still be helped. The condition is good treatment and not too late. If the conditions are met 25 percent of schizophrenics can be cured. When the symptoms have been identified, one important point to start treatment is the courage of the family to accept the reality. They also have to realize that mental disorders that require treatment so that it does not need to be connected with various beliefs (Hawari, 2014).

There are many reasons mental patients are taken to hospital to undergo treatment in hospital (Rana, 2009). Patients who show symptoms and intentions to commit suicide include a tendency to injure themselves or others, patients who need monitoring when trying new treatments, patients who need treatment that can only be done in a mental hospital and patients who experience disability in self-care are some criteria that are often found as reasons for being hospitalized. Every patient who enters the psychiatric hospital will be diagnosed with its severity. The diagnosis is based on observing the reported behavior and experience of the patient. Patients who are diagnosed with a severe mental disorder will be hospitalized. In comprehensive

inpatient management, collaboration between several medical and nursing professions is needed, starting from accepting new patients in the care unit. Nurses begin to run nursing care as a professional activity. The nurse starts by admission a new patient.

Admission of new patients is a procedure performed by nurses when there are new patients coming to an inpatient room. This activity is the first stage nurses interact with patients and families, which cannot be separated from the implementation of nursing care. Therefore, the researchers felt the need to conduct qualitative research in a phenomenological approach to the motivation of nurses in the admission of new patients at Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital Surabaya.

The general purpose of this study was to explore nurses' motivation in accepting new patients at Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital Surabaya.

The question in this study is "What are the reasons nurses carry out new patient admissions activities at Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital Surabaya?"

METHODS

Study Design

This research was conducted with a qualitative interpretive phenomenological design approach.

Setting

This study was conducted in Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital Surabaya.

Research Subject

The nurse referred to in this study is someone with a minimum education of Nursing Diploma III and has worked for at least 2 years and has conducted a process of admission to new patients. Acceptance referred to in this study is a series of activities carried out by nurses in the

process of accepting a patient who has just entered the treatment room. There were 12 participants involved in this study.

Instruments

Data collection is done by interview.

Data Analysis

The researchers performed data analysis by using thematic analysis.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from the director of Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital to get the permission. Data collection procedure started with the informed consent to participants that they were briefed about the study and kept their confidentiality.

RESULTS

From the results of interviews with 12 nurses in the inpatient room, admission of new patients or at the Menur Psychiatric Mental Hospital in Surabaya, is a continuation of the process of handling patients from the clinic, Emergency Treatment Installation or transfer from other care units.

DISCUSSION

Nurses must be able to carry out the activities of admission of new patients, because it is in accordance with the work description contained in the nursing work plan. There are already standard operating procedures governing the admission of new patients. Admission of new patients is the responsibility of the nursing team leader, but if the nursing team leader is not present, then as a member of the nursing team helps in the admission process, then the results are reported to the team leader. This process is important so that reception runs quickly and service to patients can be satisfying.

Awareness of all nurses is needed for the admission process.

There are categories of nurses in this admission process, nursing team leaders who have obligations in the admission of new patients and members of nursing team who have the awareness of assisting in the admission of new patient activities. Acceptance of new patients for nurses is a work procedure that has been written in the nursing work plan, it is the duty of the team leader to carry out this activity. This can be interpreted that the nursing team leader has competence and autonomy (Deci & Ryan, 2002). in the reception of new patients. As a consequence of the exercise of this authority, the nurse's performance is fulfilled and gets performance incentives. Conversely, if not done, the performance is not met and incentives not obtained can even give worse consequences that will get a reprimand from the boss for not being able to carry out tasks in the nursing work plan can even be considered as incompetent nursing team leaders.

For team members of nursing, admission of new patients is not his duty. But with a high awareness of the quality of nursing services, nurses doing this activity are then reported to the team leader. In this phenomenon there is a nurse's initiative to carry out activities that are not her job and then report to the authorities. There is a desire within the nurse to maintain nursing services so that she takes on the role of doing the task of the team leader who is not in place to carry out new patient admissions. In this case, maintaining social relationships with superiors is a motivational factor (Ryan, R. M., et.al, 2002). which encourages members of the nursing team to conduct new patient admission activities.

CONCLUSION

Admission of new patients is part of

patient care activities in ward. A nurse is motivated to engage in new patient admission activities influenced by two external factors, namely the existence of competence and autonomy that has the value of incentives and internal factors, namely the drive within to maintain the quality of nursing services and maintain social relations with superiors.

SUGGESTION

Mastery expertise and skills of the new admissions nurse are needed to strengthen the independence of the nursing team leader in conducting new patient admissions and the nursing team members' self-understanding of their involvement in the social environment of the patient care room to foster initiative to engage in the process of admission a new patient.

REFERENCES

- Hawari, H. D. (2014). Skizofrenia edisi ketiga pendekatan holistik (BPSS) bio-psiko-sosial-spiritual. *Jakarta: Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Indonesia.*
- Kementerian Kesehatan RI. (2019). *Riskesmas 2018, Laporan Tahunan.* Jakarta: Badan Penelitian dan Pengembangan Kesehatan.
- Rana, D., & Upton, D. (2009). *Psychology for Nurses.* New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2002). Overview of self-determination theory: An organismic dialectical perspective. *Handbook of self-determination research*, 3-33.
- Stuart, Gail W. (2016). *Keperawatan Kesehatan Jiwa Stuart, Prinsip dan Praktik.* Edisi Indonesia. Singapore: Elsevier.
- Sugiyono. (2009). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D.* Bandung: Alfabeta.

Townsend (2015). *Nursing Diagnoses in Psychiatric Nursing, Care Plans and Psychotropic Medication.* ninth edition. Philadelphia: F.A. Davis Company.